

**BASKETBOL VA STRITBOL BILAN SHUG'ULLANUVCHILARNING JISMONIY
TARBIYALASHNING SAMARALI VOSITASI SIFATIDA.**

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Annotatsiya: Yuqori sinf o'quvchilarini Basketbol va stritbol mashg'ulotlari davomida tayyorgarlik va sog'lomlashtirish darajasini oshirish uchun integral ishlatish tavsiya etiladi:

Kalit so'zlar: Sport, stritbol, basketbol, integrativ, mashg'ulot, kuch, tezkorlik, chidamlilik, texnik, taktik, to'garak, mashq, o'yin, Jismoniy salomatlik.

Аннотация: Учащиеся старших классов во время тренировки по баскетболу и стритболу Для повышения уровня подготовки и восстановления рекомендуется комплексно использовать:

Ключевые слова: Спорт, стритбол, баскетбол, интегративные, тренировочные, силовые, скоростные, выносливые, технические, тактические,

Annotation: High school students during basketball and streetball training to increase the level of preparation and recovery, it is recommended to use integrally:

Key words: Sports, streetball, basketball, integrative, training, strength, speed, endurance, technical, tactical, circle, exercise, game, Physical health.

Kirish. Yosh avlodning jismoniy faolligining etarli emasligi bugungi kunda jismoniy tarbiyaning muhim muammolaridan biri bo'lib qolmoqda. Ushbu muammoni hal etishning samarali yo'nalishi yil davomida o'smirlar va yoshlar tomonidan salomatlikni saqlash va rivojlanish ta'siriga ega bo'lgan ommabop, qiziqarli jismoniy faoliyat turlari muammoni hal etuvchi vosita sifatida xizmat qiladi. . [2, 3].

O'zbekiston Prezidentining Jismoniy tarbiya va sport to'g'risida qonunining yangi tahriri, (2015. 15. 04) Jismoniy tarbiya va Ommaviy sportni rivojlantirish to'g'risidagi qarorlari (2017. 07. 03) 2019-2023-yillar davrida O'zbekiston respublikasida jismoniy tarbiya va ommaviy sportni rivojlantirish konsepsiyasini tasdiqlash to'g'risida (2019. 13. 02.) qaror qabul qilindi. Ushbu dolzarb qaror, masalani hal qilishga qaratilgan asosiy manba bo'lib xizmat qiladi.

Tadqiqotning maqsadi – yuqori sinf o'quvchilarining basketbol va stritbol mashg'ulotlarni integrativ tarzda tashkil etish va mazmunini takomillashtirish asosida o'yin faoliyati samaradorligini oshirish.

Pedagogik tajriba davrida 15-16 yoshli o'smirlarni funktsional tayyorgarlik ko'rsatkichlarining o'sish sur'atlari.

Bundan tashqari, pedagogik eksperiment davomida tadqiqot shug'ullanuvchilarining jismoniy tayyorgarligi dinamikasi o'rganildi. Buning uchun 1000 m, 30 m ga yugurish, chiziqda tortish va joydan uzunlikka sakrash kabi testlar ishlatilgan. Sinov natijalari 2 ta nazorat guruhida ($p > 0,05$) o'rganilayotgan ko'rsatkichlarning biroz o'zgarishini ko'rsatadi. 1 nazorat va tajriba guruhlarida bu o'zgarishlar ishonchli ($p < 0,05$), ($p < 0,01$) ekanligini ko'rish mumkin. Sinov natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, 1 nazorat guruhida jismoniy tayyorgarlik darajasining pasayishi kuzatildi. Shunday qilib, guruh natijasi 1000 m yugurish, ko'rsatkichlari past 2,94% ($p < 0,05$), 30 m ga yugurish - 4,22% ($p < 0,05$), gavdani bukib yozish-7,01% ($p < 0,05$). Tajriba guruhida ushbu ko'rsatkichlar mos ravishda - 9,83% ($p < 0,01$), 21,36% ($p < 0,001$), 6,82% ($p < 0,05$).

Tadqiqot usullari va tashkil etilishi. Tadqiqot muammolarini hal qilish uchun quyidagi usullardan foydalanilgan:

Pedagogik eksperiment davomida tajriba-sinov guruhda sportchilarning jismoniy tayyorgarlik ko'rsatkichlarining o'sishi.¹

(1 jadval). Pedagogik eksperiment davomida tajriba-sinov guruhda sportchilarning jismoniy tayyorgarlik ko'rsatkichlarining o'sishi. (n = 12)

Sinov	Ko'rsatkichlar		%	t	P
	1	2			
	X±o	X±o	O'sishi		
1	2	3	4	5	6
Joydan uzunlikka sakrash (sm)	182,3±4,62	194,1±3,17	6,1	2,11	<0,05
To'ldirilgan to'pni uloqtirish (m)	5,45±0,22	6,03±0,12	9,6	2,14	<0,05
Mokisimon yugurish 5x10 m (s)	13,99±0,14	13,96±0,12	0,3	0,18	>0,05
Yarim o'tirib yurish (s)	1,64±0,05	1,5±0,04	8,5	2,07	<0,05
Oltidaqiqali yugurish (m)	1225±40,4	1254,6±38,3	2,4	0,53	>0,05
3x5 m himoya darvozasida yugurish (s)	5,51±0,09	5,45±0,08	1,1	0,47	>0,05

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1.A.A.Pulatov, F.V.Ganiyeva, B.M.Miradilov, D.T.Xusanova, F.A.Pulatov .Basketbol nazariyasi va uslubiyati /darslik: : «Sanostandart» nashriyoti, 2017-yil. 348 bet.

<https://tiame66.uz>

<https://uz-conference.com>

To'pni ikki qo'l bilan savatga tashlash (soni)	29,2±0,47	30,7±0,52	4,9	2,11	<0,05
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"Joydan uzunlikka sakrash" testida natijalar 6,1% ($t=2,11$, $P<0,05$), "o'tirgan holda joydan to'ldirilgan to'pni tashlash" - 9,6% ($t=2,14$, $p<0,05$) bilan yaxshilandi.

Ko'cha basketbolida basketbolchilarning musobaqa faoliyatining mazmuni va tarkibini tahlil qilish biz ishlab chiqqan texnikaning ta'siri ostida bir qator ijobiy o'zgarishlarni aniqladi.

Ko'rib chiqilayotgan barcha ko'rsatkichlarning qiymatlari ortdi va o'sish 3,3 dan 35,8% gacha ko'tarildi.

Ko'rib chiqilayotgan 7 ko'rsatkichlarining to'rttasida ishonchli o'zgarishlar yuz berdi. Shunday qilib, o'yinda o'zining va raqibning darvozasiga to'pning otish ko'rsatkichlari 26,5 va 35% ($t=2,07$ va $2,15$, $p<0,05$) bilan yaxshilandi. O'yin davomida basketbolchilar tomonidan ruxsat etilgan to'pni yo'qotish miqdori kamaydi. Pedagogik tajribadan so'ng, qizlar 35,8% kamroq xato qildi ($t=2,18$, $P<0,05$).

Xavfsizlik kabi taktik harakatlarning ma'lumotlari ham ishonchli tarzda o'zgardi. Tajriba-sinov guruh sinaluvchilari o'yin davomida ushbu texnikadan foydalanish hajmini 31,6% ($T=2,29$, $p<0,05$ da) bilan oshirdi.

15-16 yoshli o'smirlarni olib boriladigan tajriba davomida jismoniy tayyorgarligi dinamikasi o'rganildi. 96 kun davomida o'tkazilgan testlar shuni ko'rsatdiki, jismoniy tayyorgarlik darajasida ishonchli yaxshilanish yuz berdi. Bunga yozgi davrda sport maktablarining yosh basketbolchilari uchun mashg'ulotlarning etishmasligi tufayli yuzaga keladi. Yosh sportchilarga taqdim etilgan yuklamalama o'rtacha tezlikda amalga oshiriladigan oddiy mashqlarning katta hajmiga (50-60% dan ortiq) ega edi, bu tizim va tana funksiyalarining sezilarli javob reaksiyasiga sabab bo'lmadi va shug'ullanuvchilarning funksional imkoniyatlari sezilarli darajada oshmadi.

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